

TOMATO AND CUCUMBER VIRUS DISEASES AND CONTROL OF VECTORS

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SUMMARY: The tomatoes and cucumbers in greenhouses in Albania are of particular importance. The viruses of tomato that were found are as follows: Tomato Mosaic Virus (ToMV) and strain of internal necrosis fruit, virus strike of tomato, Cucumber Mosaic Virus in tomato (CMV), CMV-necrotic strain, CMV- strain, dwarfism of the tomato, the wilt virus with defilement of tomato fruits TSWV (Tomato Spotted Wilt Virus), Potato Virus Y in tomato (PVY). In cucumbers the detected Cucumber Mosaic Virus (CMV), Tomato virus (TSWV) are part of the quarantine list (EPPO, 2004), the presence of these viruses shows the risk of damage which is expected to be in cultivated plants. The major viruses infecting tomatoes were TSWV and ToMV followed by PVY and CMV. The incidence of TSWV virus has been increased lately so the management measures of control will be of great significance in the future. The major virus infecting cucumber was CMV. The treatment with insecticides has reduced aphid populations.

Key words: virus, monitoring, vector, ELISA, control.

INTRODUCTION

The cucumber and tomato cultivation in greenhouses in Albania is increasing, due to the tradition of their being widely used by our customers. The area under greenhouses planted with these crops was 731 and 728 ha in 2008 and 2009, respectively. Main crops is tomato (57.8%) and cucumber (23.7%) (Statistical Yearbook, 2009). There is increased vegetable production, especially under plastic covers. However, most farms are still small and fragmented, and use old production systems (Finetti-Sialer, 2005).

Vegetable production is affected by many diseases, some of which are of great

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economic importance. Tomato production has suffered from many pests and disease problems, including those caused by viruses which substantially reduce yield and quality (Golnaraghi et al., 2004).

A recent survey on fungal diseases showed the presence of several diseases of Solanaceae and Cucurbitaceae (Merkuri et al., 2002), but so far there have been no reports on the presence of virus diseases of vegetables in Albania. In this context, an investigation was carried out in the greenhouses in the central part of our country and the results are reported in this paper. The yield and quality of tomatoes and cucumbers cultivated in greenhouses is decreasing due to infections from viral diseases. The symptoms produced by different viruses on tomato cultivars include leaf and fruit deformations, stunting, necrosis of stems and leaves, vein discoloration, general yellowing of leaves, systemic chlorotic and necrotic leaf spots, general mosaic and mottle on leaves, purple leaf veins, vessel browning, development of light green concentric spots with black centers on immature fruits, yellow spot discolorations on ripe fruits and subsequent wilting and complete collapse of plants (Choi et al., 2004; Jeon et al., 2006; Lee et al., 2007; Lee et al., 2008; Oh et al., 2008).

The most important viruses affecting these cultures, the incidence of viral diseases and also vectors such as *Franklinella occidentalis* (EPPO 2004) are defined.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Surveys were conducted in the years 2008 and 2009 in greenhouses, especially in the intense area, periodically during plant vegetation for the appearance of symptoms caused by diseases and pests. The study was focused on determining the viral diseases that affect tomato and cucumber cultures. The survey was done in greenhouses in the following sites: Peza - Tirana, Shën – Vlash in Durrës, Lushnja, Fushë - Krujë and Mbrostar - Gërcalli of Fier District, during 2008 - 2009.

The leaf and fruit samples were collected from symptomatic plants of tomatoes and cucumbers grown under above mentioned greenhouses according to BBCH-scale (solaneous fruit) Feller (1995), in principal growth stage 5- 8.

The virus-like symptoms most frequently observed were mottle, mosaic, stunting and necrosis. The plants with symptoms were sampled and tested for the presence of viruses in the Laboratory of Viruses in the Department of Plant Protection. The determination of viruses was done by serologic method of ELISA test (Clark and Adams, 1977), by taking taken tomato and cucumber samples, 206 and 50 samples respectively.

ELISA employs polyclonal antisera to trap and monoclonal antisera for detection. Microtitre plates (Nunc Maxisorp Immunoplate) were used. The known infected plants, together with healthy plants of the same species were used as positive control while the test plants were practically used as negative control. Dilute the coating antibody 1000 times in coating buffer. Bring 200 µl of the antibody solution in the wells of the ELISA plate. Cover the plate with a lid and place the plate in a humid box (wet tissue on the bottom of the box). Close the box and incubate the box over-night in the refrigerator at 4 °C or 3 hours at 37 °C. Wash the plate in the plate washer with the washing buffer: 3 washings per plate. Prepare 2 dilutions of plant extract samples in SEB; undiluted sample and 1/10. Dilute the positive control 10 times in SEB. Bring 200 µl of the solutions in the wells of the ELISA plate. Fill 3 wells with the positive control and 3 wells with the negative control. Cover the plate with a lid and place the plate in a humid box.

Close the box and incubate the box over-night in the refrigerator at 4 °C. Wash the plate in the plate washer with the washing buffer: 4 soakings and washings per plate. Dilute the AP conjugate 1000 times in SEB. Bring 200 µl of the conjugate solution in the wells of the ELISA plate. Cover the plate with a lid and place the plate in a humid box. Close the box and incubate the box over-night in the refrigerator at 4 °C or 3 hours at 37 °C. Wash the plate in the plate washer with the washing buffer: 4 soakings and washings per plate. Prepare the substrate (fresh). Bring 200 µl of the substrate in each well of the ELISA plate. Cover the plate with a lid and incubate the plate at room temperature until the positive control and positive samples are coloring yellow. This may take 15 minutes to several hours depending on the concentration of the virus in the samples and the reactivity of the antibodies. Read the plate in the plate reader (405 nm) after 60 minutes of incubation.

Monitoring for the presence of viruses was done in cultivars of tomato planted as the first and cucumber planted as the second crop in greenhouses. The tomatoes cultivars were: Siluete, Platus, Dellos, Jon, Viktor, Berila, Gabriela, 12.07, Bonita and the cucumber cultivars were: Magnum, SG.

Starting from the data on the presence of viruses the vectors for these viruses such as aphids and the presence of trips *Frankliniella occidentalis* and *Thrips tabaci* (EPPO, 2004) were taken into consideration.

Blue/yellow CSALOMON® sticky traps were installed in the above greenhouses. In addition, samples of flowers of tomatoes and cucumbers in greenhouses were collected weekly. The identification of the thrips was based on the EPPO Diagnostic protocol for *Frankliniella occidentalis* (Chatzivassiliou et.al, 2000) and the confirmation by Dr Steve. The characteristics of the CSALOMON® trap (based on tests performed in Hungary): the western flower thrips are predominantly attracted to the blue part of the trap.

Other thrips (e.g. *Thrips tabaci*) are more readily attracted to the yellow part. In this trap type insects are attracted by the visual cue of the bright color of the trap. The trap remains effective as long as the sticky surface is not totally covered by captured insects. This usually happens only after 6-8 weeks of exposure, unless there is a mass outbreak in the glasshouse.

The main pesticides that were used: Nurelle (*chlorpyrifos* + *cypermethrin*), Mos-pilan (*acetamipride*), Mesurol (*methiocarb*), etc.

RESULTS

The monitoring was done in the in principal growth stage 5 - 8 of the tomato crop and cucumber plant. The 206 and 50 samples with symptoms for the presence of viruses were analyzed.

The analysis showed the presence of the following viruses in tomatoes: ToMV, CMV, TSWV, and PVY. Some strains of these viruses (CMV necrotic) were detected in our country for the first time. CMV virus was present in the cucumber plant as well. The symptoms were observed and the macroscopic analysis showed that viruses were the cause of these signs. The infected tomato plants were characterized by a light- and dark-green mottling and malformation of leaves. Other symptoms were plant stunting, fruit ripening, and reduced fruit. As mentioned above, the results show that in our tomato culture the severity of viral diseases depend on the cultivars. TSWV, which has several strains (at least 9 species of *Thrips*, *Frankliniella* and *Scirtothrips*) is the virus

transmitted by thrips: the viruses' incidence; number of plants with symptoms in cv. Siluete (TSWV infection by the virus) is up to 19%. This is due to the growth of aphid populations early in April, where the presence of the vector Trips (*Frankliniella occidentalis*) was found (Çota and Merkuri, 2004).

Also, the cucumber mosaic virus (CMV) in tomatoes displays a higher incidence in cv. Dellos going up to 12%, especially when we have differences in temperatures. When the temperatures increase over 24 °C, these symptoms for the virus disappear. The cucumber mosaic virus (CMV) is present in cucumber culture so in the SG and Magnum cultivars the incidence of this virus reaches up to 7% (Graph 1-2).

Graph1. Percentage of virus infected tomato plants

The major viruses infecting tomato were TSWV and ToMV followed by PVY and CMV.

Graph 2. Percentage of virus infected cucumbers plants

DISCUSSION

The major virus infecting cucumber was CMV. On some farms it is noted that the control of these diseases caused by viruses is done with pesticides. This comes from the symptoms of viral diseases and in some cases there are similarities with other pathogens. This endangers the safety of consumers and the environment.

Defining viruses in these cultures is a contribution to better knowledge how to organize the control of vectors, as transmitters of the viral diseases, in the future. There are different methods for controlling aphids (*Myzus persicae* Sulzer) and trips (*Frankliniella occidentalis*), all of them relying on the use of chemicals, ranging from 12-14/vegetative season.

The following plant protection products have been: commercial: organic - azadirachtin (neem), horticultural oil, insecticidal soap, Mycotrol (fungus), pyrethrins etc. conventional - acetamiprid (Assail), bifenthrin (Brigade), beta-cyfluthrin (Baythroid), esfenvalerate (Asana), dinotefuran (Scorpion), flonicamid (Beleaf), imidacloprid (Provado), malathion, spirotetramat (Movento), thiamethoxam (Actara), zeta-cypermethrin (Mustang), and many more. Home Use Organic products + acetamiprid, bifenthrin, esfenvalerate, imidacloprid, malathion.

It is noted that chemical treatments are not conducted on the basis of the curve of the flight of these insects - vectors, based on the diagnosis and occurrence. It will be assumed that critical levels of aphids are reached 5–10 aphids, mostly wingless, detected per 100 leaves. As a result of intensive chemical treatments that may cause the disappearance of the natural enemies, an increase in aphid population has been observed (Musa et al., 2004). According to some authors (Ruffle and Miller 2002; Epstein et al., 2000), the intensive use of broad-spectrum insecticides contributes to reduce the presence of aphids' natural enemies and increase the environmental pollution and the risk for the customer.

CONCLUSION

In this study, the incidence and distribution of four viruses in the main greenhouses of tomatoes and cucumbers production in Albania is documented. In the tomato plant, the results of serological tests have the presence of new virus strains of ToMV (Tomato Mosaic Virus), such as necrotic strain and aucuba - ToMV. There are also unnoticed previously new strains of CMV virus in tomato for example. CMV - necrotic, CMV - dwarfism of tomato.

These indicate the risk of performance of these viruses in the cultivated tomato plants in greenhouse as well as in the field. The spreading threat is vicious virus of tomato fruits wither. Tomato spotted wilt virus (TSWV), which in some varieties ranges up to 19% and is found in the presence of the vector of dissemination of these viral diseases. Also from serological tests in the tomato plant, the presence of potato virus Y is noted, a virus which has been found in our country for the first time. In cucumber culture, in the SG and Magnum cultivar the mosaic virus CMV is present, the intensity of which reaches up to 7%.

The results presented here suggest that tomato and cucumber viruses' infections should be of special concern to farmers, and they present potential threats to tomato production. For this reason, additional work on characterization of tomato and cucum-

ber viruses, their modes of transmission and best means of their management should be carried out further. Considering that vegetable production is a priority for Albanian agriculture, measures should urgently be taken to avoid the introduction and spread of new and emerging viruses.

REFERENCES

- CHATZIVASSILIOU, E.K., WEEKES, R., MORRIS, J., WOOD, K.R., BARKER, I., KATIS, N.I.: Tomato spotted wilt virus (TSWV) in Greece: its incidence following the expansion of *Frankliniella occidentalis*, and characterisation of isolates collected from various hosts. *Annals of Applied Biology*, 137:127–134, 2000.
- CHOI, G. S., KIM, J. H., KIM, J. S., CHOI, J. K.: Characterization of Cucumber mosaic virus isolated from Water chickweed (*Stellaria aquatica*). *Plant Pathology Journal*, 20:131–134, 2004.
- CLARK, M.F., ADAMS, A.N.: Characteristics of the microplate method of enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay for the detection of plant viruses. *Journal of General Virology*, 34:475–483, 1977.
- ÇOTA, E., MERKURI, J.: Introduction of *Frankliniella occidentalis* and occurrence of Tomato spotted wilt tospovirus in Albania. *Eppo Bulletin*, 2004.
- EPSTEIN, D. L., ZACK, R.S., BRUNNER, J.F., GUT, J., BROWN, J.J: Effects of broad-spectrum insecticides on epigeal arthropod diversity in Pacific Northwest apple orchards. *Environmental Entomology*, 29:340–348, 2000.
- FELLER, C.; BLEIHOLDER, H., BUHR, L., HACK, H., HESS, M., KLOSE, R., MEIER, U., STAUSS, R., VAN DEN BOOM, T., WEBER, E. b: Phänologische Entwicklungsstadien von Gemüsepflanzen: II. Fruchtgemüse und Hülsenfrüchte. *Nachrichtenbl. Deut. Pflanzenschutzd.*, 47:217–232, 1995.
- FINETTI-SIALER, M., MERKURI, J., TAURO, G., MYRTA, A., GALLITELLI, D.: Viruses of vegetable crops in Albania. 2005.
- GOLNARAGHI, A.R., SHAHRAEEN, N., POURRAHIM, S.H., GHASEMI, A.: Occurrence and relative incidence of viruses infecting soybeans in Iran. *Plant Disease*, 88:1069–1074, 2004.
- JEON, Y.W., HONG, J. S., LEE, S.Y., RYU, K.H., CHOI, J. K.: Characterization of an isolate of Cucumber mosaic virus isolated from *Canna generalis* Bailey. *Plant Disease Research*, 12:298–302, 2006.
- LEE, J.A., CHOI, S.K., YOON, J.Y., HONG, J.S., RYU, K.H., LEE, S.Y., CHOI, J.K.: Variation in the pathogenicity of lily isolates of Cucumber mosaic virus. *Journal of Plant Pathology*, 23:251–259, 2007.
- LEE, H. G., KIM, S.R., JEON, Y.W., KWON, S.B., RYU, K.H., CHOI, K.J.: Identification and characterization of three isolates of Cucumber mosaic virus isolated from weed hosts. *Plant Disease Research*, 14:15–20, 2008.
- MERKURI, J., VARAKU, S., CASULLI, F.: Fungal diseases of vegetable crops in Albania. *Phytopathologia Mediterranea*, 41:157–159, 2002.
- MERKURI, J.: *Virusi dhe Bima*, 126–137, 2007.
- MUSA, F., CARLI, C., SUSURI, L., PIREVA I.: Monitoring of *Myzus persicae* (Sulzer) in potato fields in Kosovo, *Acta Agriculturae Slovenica*, 83-2: 379 – 385, 2004.
- OH, S. M., KIM, S. R., HONG, J. S., RYU, K. H., LEE, G. P., CHOI, J. K.: Characteriza-

tion of an isolate of Cucumber mosaic virus isolated from Chinese aster (*Callistephus chinensis*). *Plant Disease Research*, 14:229–232, 2008.

RUFFLE, R., MILLER, J.: Digging for alternatives: an analysis of potato pest management research at two

Northwest land grant universities. Northwest Coalition for Alternatives to Pesticides, Eugene, OR, 2002.

STATISTICAL YEARBOOK, Ministry of Agriculture, Food, and Consumer Protection, 2009.

VIRUSNA OBOLJENJA PARADAJZA I KRSTAVCA I SUZBIJANJE VEKTORA VIRUSA

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Izvod

Virusna oboljenja krastavca i paradajza predstavljaju značajan ograničavajući činitelj proizvodnje u zaštićenom prostoru u Albaniji. Proučavanjem prouzročivača oboljenja na paradajzu utvrđeni su sojevi virusa mozaika paradajza (Tomato mosaic virus - ToMV), virusa mozaika krastavca (Cucumber mosaic virus -CMV), virusa bronzavosti paradajza (Tomato spotted wilt virus- TSWV) i virusa crtičastog mozaika krompira (Potato virus Y). Na krastavcu opisani su virus mozaika krastavca (Cucumber mosaic virus-CMV, i virus bronzavosti paradajza (Tomato spotted wilt virus -TSWV). Po intenzitetu oboljenja na paradajzu najznačajniji su bili virusa bronzavosti paradajza i virus mozaika paradajza, nakon toga su po značaju sledili virus crtičastog mozaika krompira i virus mozaika krastavca. Na krastavcu najveće smanjenje prinosa prouzrokuje virus mozaika krastavca. Insekticidni tretman je značajno smanjio populaciju vektora- lisnih vaši.

Ključne reči: virusi, monitoring, vektor, ELISA, kontrola.

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